

**Dr. B. R. Ambedkar's Contribution
to Women Empowerment
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ABSTRACT:

This Paper Focuses on Dr. B. R. Ambedkar Views on Women Empowerment, he was a fighter for the dignity of women and depressed people. Being a pioneer of Social Justice, he always functioned for the empowerment and betterment of women's life. According To Babasaheb Ambedkar Everybody Should Be Treated Equally Irrespective of Caste, Creed, Gender and Religion. That's Why He Started Working for The Liberation of Women and Their Rights. This Paper focus on The Thoughts of Dr. B.R. Ambedkar towards women, he strongly believed that women empowerment can be achieved by welfare of women, the activities of empowering women worldwide should follow the vision of Dr. B.R. Ambedkar.

KEYWORDS:

Women Empowerment, Gender equality, Social Justice.

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Introduction:

Empowerment refers to increasing the political, social and economic strength of individuals and communities. Empowerment and autonomy of women and the improvement of their political, social, economic and health status is highly important and it is necessary for the achievement of sustainable human development.

According to Dr.B.R.Ambedkar Gender equality, leaderships, gender main streaming, networking, and financial freedom are the essential aspects of women empowerment, and he realized this at his time and included it in the process of social reforms.

Dr. B. R. Ambedkar started working for the struggle of women for eradication of caste systems and upliftment of the underprivileged sections. He realized this could not be achieved without liberating the women themselves. He motivated women and depressed class and addressed them to participate in struggle against cast prejudices. He encouraged women to

organize themselves in society. He told women to be progressive and abolish traditionalism, ritualism and customary habits, which were threat to their progress.

Empowerment is nothing but a developing and increasing capacities of individuals, communities to make them part of the main stream of society. Education is the only mean by which societies grow out of oppression to democratic participation and involvement. It is a powerful tool for empowerment of individual. Over the generation, marginalized sections and women in Indian society were denied the opportunity to education. DR.B.R.Ambedkar put all his efforts to guarantee the educational opportunities to all the citizens of India.

Dr.B.R.Ambedkar was an architect of Indian constitution. He provided strong constitutional safeguards to women for their empowerment. He always believed in the ability of women, and he thought that if the women from all walks of life are taken into confidence, they may play a significant role in the social reforms, they have played massive and active role to eradicate the social abuses, he insisted that every married women must participate in her husband's activities as a friend. But women must have to show the courage to fight against the inequality and deny the life of slaves. she should insist on the principle of equality, if all the women follow it, they will get the real respect and create their own identity.

Women Empowerment in the eyes of Dr. B. R. Ambedkar:

Dr. B. R. Ambedkar a determined fighter and a well-known scholar has made significant efforts to lead the society on the path of liberty, equality, and fraternity. He is the first Indian to break down the barriers in the way of advancement of women in India. He stated that women should be given all round development more importantly education, their wellbeing and socio-cultural rights. He emphasized that each and every section of Indian women should be given their due share of rights.

Dr. B. R. Ambedkar started his movement in 1920. He stated that 'We shall see better days soon and our progress will be greatly accelerated if male education is persuaded side by side with female education,' he put stress on the gender equality and the need for education and exposed the problems of the depressed as well as women.

Dr. B. R. Ambedkar always believed in the strength of women and their role in the process of social reform. Addressing another meeting of

women, he said, I measure the progress of community by the degree of progress which women had achieved. Let every girl who marries stand by her husband, claim to be her husband's friend and equal and refuse to be his slave, I am sure if you follow this advice, you will bring honour and glory to yourself". He emphasises on reconstruction of the society on the basis of equality. This shows how Ambedkar created awareness among poor, illiterate women and inspired them to fight against the unjust and social practices like child marriages and devadasi system etc.

Dr. B. R. Ambedkar exclaimed, "I strongly believe in the movements run by women. If they are truly taken into confidence, they may change the present picture of society which is very miserable. In past, they have played a significant role in improving the condition of weaker section and classes". He always honoured women for their work and hardships. He spent his life for the betterment of women, Being India's first law minister and chairman of drafting committee of the constitution, Dr. B. R. Ambedkar's dream was to make free women from the age-old thralldom by reforming the social laws created by Manu. He therefore, took initiative to draft and introduce the Hindu code bill in the constituent assembly.

Dr. B. R. Ambedkar tried an adequate inclusion of Women's right in the Political Vocabulary and Constitution of India

- Article 14–Equal rights and opportunities in political, economic and social spares.
- Article 15–prohibits discrimination on the ground of sex.
- Article 15(3)–enables affirmative discrimination in favour of women.
- Article 39–equal means of livelihood and equal pay for equal work.
- Article 42–human conditions of work and maternity relief.
- Article 51(a) (c)– fundamental duties to renounce practices, derogatory to the dignity of women.
- Article 46– the state to promote with special care, the educational and economic interest of weaker section of people and to protect them from social injustice and all forms of exploitation.
- Article 47– the state to raise the level of nutrition and standard of living of its people and the improvement of public health and so on.
- Article 243D (3), 243T (3) and 243R (4)– provides for allocation of seats in the panchayati Raj system.

The Hindu code bill, the most formidable legislative measure of modern India, sought among other reforms, to put an end to a variety of marriage system prevailing in India and legalize only monogamous marriages. This bill also sought to confer the right to property and adoption. It put men and women on an equal level in all legal matters.

The Hindu Code Bill was later split into four bills, The Hindu marriage act 1955; the Hindu Succession act 1956; The Hindu Minority and guardianship act 1956 and The Hindu Adoption and maintenance act 1956 are the four enactments which incorporate the ideas and principles of Hindu Code Bill formulated by Dr. B. R. Ambedkar. They give independent status to women and endow them with the right of adoption, succession and property, it is contribution of Dr. B. R. Ambedkar.

Objectives of The Study:

The present Research paper focused on the following objectives

1. To study the contribution of Dr. B. R. Ambedkar for the upliftment and empowerment of Indian women after Independence.
2. Highlight the efforts of Dr. B. R. Ambedkar for the empowerment of women.

Research Method of Study:

This paper is descriptive and analytical in nature. this paper is an attempt to study the contribution of Dr. B. R. Ambedkar towards women empowerment in India. The data is collected from secondary sources for this study, by Internet, Government documents, newspapers, published papers, books.

Conclusion:

Dr. B. R. Ambedkar's aim for the society is based on gender equality is yet to be comprehended and therefore his beliefs are important for the society that favours women empowerment. He had a philanthropic view towards all the women, irrespective of their caste, religion and class. Looking into the views of Dr. B. R. Ambedkar it clearly shows that equality should be made available to all persons even in socio-economic life through state's intervention. It can be achieved through the means of reservation of seats in educational institutions and public employment, as provided under the ambit of Indian Constitution. In Contemporary setup the Indian Women have achieved a lot in various spheres of their life

though they are still in the vicious grips of various social tribulations like prostitution, rape, domestic violence, and victims of acid attack etc. Despite all these evils women are holding high positions of authority in all the walks of life including, administration, Defence Academy, Medical, Engineering, Higher Education, Politics, Sports, Foreign Services, Industry and Trade etc. It Would be worth mentioning the quote of Dr. B. R. Ambedkar's 'Unity is meaningless without the accompaniment of women, Education is fruitless without educated women, and agitation is incomplete without the strength of women'.

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Conflict of interest:

The Authors have no conflict of interest to declare that they are relevant to the content of this article.

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